

Development of a Conceptual, Task, and Assessment Model Measuring Clinical Judgment

William Muntean & Joe Betts

National Council of State Boards of Nursing (NCSBN)

Chicago, IL

Overview

- Development of an R&D framework for investigating the measurement of clinical judgment.
- Elaborate on the foundations of clinical judgment in the nursing practice.
- Methods used to make guide the item development process for measuring clinical judgment.
- Final framework for building and reviewing clinical judgment items and scenarios.

R&D Framework for Measuring CJ

Focus on

1st Steps: Review Literature on CJ in Nursing

- Literature Review on Nursing Clinical Decision-Making (Muntean, 2012)
- NCSBN[®] & American Institutes of Research (AIR) collaboration (2013-2014)
 - Functional Job Analysis
 - Strategic Job Analysis
 - Linkage Workshop

Review of the Status of CJ

- Clinical judgment is seen as a vital aspect of entry-level nursing.
- Numerous studies found that patient progress and safety is negatively impacted by poor clinical judgment skills.
- Clinical judgment skills are becoming more importance as client population seen by entry-level nurses becomes more critically acute.
- As the developers of the licensure examination for entry-level nurses, we needed to identify how to measure CJ in a reliable and valid manner.

Literature Review

- Comprehensive evaluation of the status of research into the use, development, and education related to CJ in nursing
- Outlined 3 major areas:
 - The impact of poor clinical judgment on patient care.
 - Aspects of the research that suggested exogenous and endogenous factors affecting nursing outcomes i.e., time pressure increases odds of poor outcomes.
 - How educational establishments approach CJ and what are the main problem-solving models used.

Clinical Judgment

- Higher-order cognitive construct
 - Challenging to define (Dickison, et al., 2016, Muntean, 2014)
- Accepted Models for Nursing Clinical Judgement
 - Information Processing Model (see Elstein, Shulman, Sprafka, & Allal, 1978; Dickison et al., 2016; Dickison, Haerling, & Lasater 2018)
 - Humanistic-Intuitive Model (Benner 1982)
 - Cognitive Continuum Model (Hammond, 1981; Harbison, 2001)
- These informed the CJ Measurement Model (CJMM)

CJ Measurement Model

1st Steps: Strategic Practice Analysis

- Developed a practice analysis to fully evaluate the knowledge, skills, and abilities of entry level nurses
 - Also identified all technology assets used in the care of patient
- NCSBN & American Institutes of Research (AIR) collaboration
 - Identify the core RN requirements
 - Gather updated list of job duties and tasks
 - Document tools and equipment utilized
- Methods:
 - Functional Job Analysis
 - Strategic Job Analysis
 - Health care facility site visits
 - Job analysis survey
 - **Linkage workshop**
 - ***Rate cross-tab of KSA and tasks by job duty***

High level Overview/Summary

- Two environmental scans: Identify requirements of entry-level nursing and tools used in the workplace
 - Review recent practice analyses from NCSBN (2009, 2010)
 - U.S. Department of Labor's O*NET
 - Fleishman's taxonomy of human abilities
 - Structured interviews with 18 RN clinicians, educators, and regulators
- Site visits across 4 U.S. regions including 127 RNs across 12 practice care settings
 - Conducted observation of daily work, focus groups, and 1:1 structured interviews
- Nationally representative job analysis survey (N = 2,522)
 - Over 25 practice care settings, all 50 U.S. states and 5 U.S. Territories, & from less than 1 year to 45 years of experience
 - Provided rating data (frequency, importance, & criticality) on tasks and abilities needed for entry-level practice
- Four, three-day focus groups comprised of 8-10 RN SMEs across more than 10 practice care settings to gather evidence on
 - Duties, tasks, knowledge, skills, and other personal characteristics
 - Key judgments needed for entry-level and associated consequences of errors
 - Health care trends
- Six linkage workshops with
 - More than 65 RN SMEs across more than 20 practice care settings from 33 U.S. states with 2 to 45 years of experience
 - Rated the extent to which each knowledge and skill was required for performing each nursing task

Final Job Requirements from Job Analyses

- 286 task statements categorized into 11 duty areas
- 165 knowledge statements categorized into 24 groups
- 65 skills categorized into 10 groups
- 75 abilities, e.g. oral comprehension
- 54 personal characteristics, e.g. willingness to work in a fast-paced environment
- 137 tools & equipment used
- 38 emerging health care trends
 - Example: aging population, cross-state licensing, etc.
- 76 key judgments
 - Example: prioritize daily tasks, when to seek help, etc.
- 69 consequences of errors
 - Example: decline in client health, increased length of stay, etc.

Linkage: Rate KSA by Tasks

		RN Tasks for Duty E			
		E1	E2	E3	E4
<p><i>To what extent is the knowledge required in order to accomplish the task?</i></p> <p>0 – Not Relevant for Performing the Task 1 – Helpful for Performing the Task 2 – Essential for Performing the Task DK – Don't Know</p>		Discuss reproductive or sexual issues with client, such as family planning, menopause, erectile dysfunction, or gender identity.	Identify client immunization needs.	Perform routine, comprehensive health assessment.	Perform a targeted screening assessments, such as scoliosis, hearing, or vision.
Knowledge Statements	Knowledge Topics				
Skills		1	2	1	1
		1	1	2	1
		2	2	1	1
	Combating lateral violence)				

Highest Rated across all Tasks

Knowledge/Skills	% of Linked Tasks
Knowledge	
Communication	29.0%
<i>Nursing Process</i>	23.8%
Professional Responsibilities	23.1%
Skills	
<i>Clinical Judgment</i>	46.5%
Professional Communication	44.1%
Active Listening	38.5%
<i>Problem Solving</i>	34.3%
<i>Critical Thinking</i>	33.9%
Therapeutic Communication	32.2%

Overlap between Skills

Note. Clinical Judgment = CJ; Critical Thinking = CT; Problem Solving = PS

More Results

- Of the 11 duty areas that organized the 286 tasks, clinical judgment itself was important for 8 (~75%)
- On a scale of 1 to 5, with 5 being most important, all three of the skills had an average importance rating of at least 4.4
- Over 80% of the nurses responding indicated that all three of these skills are needed for early-career nurses

Recent Validation

Betts, J., Muntean, W., & Dickison, P. (2024). Evaluating the importance of clinical judgment in entry-level nursing. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 63(3), 156-162.

- Large sample of SME believed CJ was necessary for entry-level
 - 57% indicated within the 1st six months, and
 - 92% indicated that it's needed within the 1st year of practice.
- 133 of entry-level tasks indicated CJ as a necessary skill
 - High percentage in areas like managing and providing care, and
 - Lower percentage in areas like operating technology/equipment and charting health data.

NCSBN. (2022). 2021 RN Practice Analysis: U.S. & Canada. Research Brief 81. NCSBN. Chicago, IL. – available on NCSBN public website

- 131 out of 146 entry-level tasks rated CJ as important or necessary underlying skill
- 45 of those skills were rated ≥ 3.5 on a Likert scale with 3 = important and 4 = necessary

Building Items & Evolving Scenarios

- Results of the practice analyses and the linkage study provided evidence of the basis for entry-level nursing work
- Results of the literature review provided the justification for the CJMM
- Putting these together resulted in a systematic method for developing both single, standalone CJ items and evolving scenarios
- Evolving scenarios:
 - Throughout the background research leading to the understanding of the conceptual model it was clear that single items were not appropriate for fully representing the utilization of CJ
 - Patient scenarios of an evolving nature were consistently identified as representations of the daily work of nurses
 - Therefore, patient scenarios were developed with items for each of the specific cognitive elements that embody CJ skills

Task Model Development

Using the practice analysis and the CJMM to build items and scenarios

Betts, J., Muntean, W., Kim, D., Jorion, N., & Dickison, P. (2019). Building a method for writing clinical judgment items for entry-level nursing exams. *Journal of Applied Testing Technology*, 20(S2), 21-39.

Task Model

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 3)	Expected Behavior(s) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.
Recognize Cues		Recognize abnormal vs normal	Environment Cues:	
		Recognize signs and symptoms	Patient Observation Cues:	
		Identify history of	Medical Record Cues:	
			Time Pressure Cues:	Rationale
		Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No		

Task Model

		Scenario	
Recognize Cues		Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 3)	
Identify history of		Expected Behavior(s) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	
Recognize signs and symptoms		Recognize abnormal vs normal	
Patient Observation Cues:		Environment Cues:	
Medical Record Cues:		Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	
Time Pressure Cues:		Rationale	
Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No		Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.	
Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.			

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 3)	Expected Behavior(s) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.	
	Recognize Cues	Recognize abnormal vs normal	Environment Cues:		
		Recognize signs and symptoms	Patient Observation Cues:		
		Identify history of	Medical Record Cues:		
				Time Pressure Cues:	Rationale
Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.				

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 3)	Expected Behavior(s) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.	
	Analyze Cues	Connection between pathophysiology and client presentation:	Requires knowledge of:		
		Use findings/observations to determine client needs:		Rationale	
				Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 3)	Expected Behavior(s) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.		
	Prioritize Hypothesis	Prioritize (likelihood, risk, etc)	Requires knowledge of:			
			Indicate Resources:	Rationale		
				Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.	

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 3)	Expected Behavior(s) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.	
	Generate Solutions	Things to address:	Requires knowledge of:		
		Things to avoid:		Rationale	
				Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 3)	Expected Behavior(s) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.		
	Take Action	Request:	Requires knowledge of and experience with:			
		Administer:				
		Perform (Skill):				
		Document:				
		Communicate			Rationale	
				Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.	

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 3)	Expected Behavior(s) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.	
	Evaluate Outcomes	Reassess:	Requires knowledge of and experience with:		
				Rationale	
				Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 1)	Regulated Behaviors	Checklist/Paradigm (Layer 2)	Items
Recognize Cues		Recognize cues from various sources to provide information for each patient.	Performance Cues	Rules to be reported/indicated to help generate ideas. Must be done with my partner (%). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.
		Recognize signs and symptoms.	Pattern Observation Cues	
		Identify history of	Medical Record Cues	
			Team Process Cues	Behavioral: Social values about autonomy, privacy, dignity, or respectful care.

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 1)	Regulated Behaviors	Checklist/Paradigm (Layer 2)	Items
Analyze Cues		Adjust cognitive filter to ensure pertinent information for each patient.	Requires knowledge of	Rules to be reported/indicated to help generate ideas. Must be done with my partner (%). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.
		Use challenge information to determine client needs.		Behavioral: Social values about autonomy, privacy, dignity, or respectful care.

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 1)	Regulated Behaviors	Checklist/Paradigm (Layer 2)	Items
Prioritize Hypotheses		Filter information based on cues.	Requires knowledge of	Rules to be reported/indicated to help generate ideas. Must be done with my partner (%). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.
		Identify relevant cues.		Behavioral: Social values about autonomy, privacy, dignity, or respectful care.

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 1)	Regulated Behaviors	Checklist/Paradigm (Layer 2)	Items
Generate Solutions		Identify cues from various sources to provide information for each patient.	Requires knowledge of	Rules to be reported/indicated to help generate ideas. Must be done with my partner (%). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.
		Change in status.		Behavioral: Social values about autonomy, privacy, dignity, or respectful care.

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 1)	Regulated Behaviors	Checklist/Paradigm (Layer 2)	Items
Take Actions		Recognize cues from various sources to provide information for each patient.	Requires knowledge of	Rules to be reported/indicated to help generate ideas. Must be done with my partner (%). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.
		Recognize signs and symptoms.		Behavioral: Social values about autonomy, privacy, dignity, or respectful care.
		Identify history of		

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 1)	Regulated Behaviors	Checklist/Paradigm (Layer 2)	Items
Evaluate Outcomes		Adjust cognitive filter to ensure pertinent information for each patient.	Requires knowledge of	Rules to be reported/indicated to help generate ideas. Must be done with my partner (%). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.
		Use challenge information to determine client needs.		Behavioral: Social values about autonomy, privacy, dignity, or respectful care.

Item Development Process

Subject Matter Experts Write & Review Items

Item Development Framework

Item Writing Framework

- Item writing panels comprised 6-24 SMEs
- Facilitators provide ...
 - Clinical judgment construct definition
 - Definitions of layer 3 & 4 components
 - Task model templates
 - Practical examples and developed items

Item Writing Framework

- SMEs filled out the task model templates

Scenario	Clinical Judgment Element (Layer 3)	Expected Behavior(s) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.		
	Recognize Cues	Recognize abnormal vs normal	Environment Cues:			
		Recognize signs and symptoms	Patient Observation Cues:			
		Identify history of	Medical Record Cues:		Rationale	
				Time Pressure Cues:	Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.

Scenario & Item Writing Guidelines

- Scenarios must be realistic (high fidelity and mapped to task statements)
- Appropriate for entry-level nurse
- Items must measure the specific CJ element (training is provided)
- MR preferred (MC ok)
 - Provide at least 6 response options per item
- Keys and distractors should be realistic
- Distractors could reflect:
 - common errors associated with this scenario
 - misconceptions about the topic
 - critical misunderstandings and/or unsafe practices
 - wrong associations with similar concepts
- The items all must refer to the scenario
- Other rules will apply for specific clinical judgment steps

Item Review Process

- Verifying entry-level content high-fidelity/authentic
- Appropriate for entry-level
- Current practice
- Items aligned with each clinical judgement step
- Answer key correct
- Avoid queuing across items in a set
- In scenarios, ensure that subsequent items have logical continuation options for incorrect responses

Item Finalization

- The scenarios and item sets from the item writing/review panels were developed into final items in different item/response format (or types)
- The next presentation will provide more details on a number of different item/response types that measure CJ elements

Scenario	Client Population Element (Case #)	Expected Behaviors	Client/Staff/Partner Element (Case #)	Client
Recognize cues	Recognize abnormal vs normal	Recognize abnormal vs normal	Recognize abnormal vs normal	Recognize abnormal vs normal
	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms	Recognize signs and symptoms
	Identify source of	Identify source of	Identify source of	Identify source of

Scenario	Client Population Element (Case #)	Expected Behaviors	Client/Staff/Partner Element (Case #)	Client
Analyze cues	Analyze cues	Analyze cues	Analyze cues	Analyze cues

Scenario	Client Population Element (Case #)	Expected Behaviors	Client/Staff/Partner Element (Case #)	Client
Plan	Plan	Plan	Plan	Plan

Scenario	Client Population Element (Case #)	Expected Behaviors	Client/Staff/Partner Element (Case #)	Client
Implement	Implement	Implement	Implement	Implement

Scenario	Client Population Element (Case #)	Expected Behaviors	Client/Staff/Partner Element (Case #)	Client
Evaluate	Evaluate	Evaluate	Evaluate	Evaluate

Scenario	Client Population Element (Case #)	Expected Behaviors	Client/Staff/Partner Element (Case #)	Client
Outcome	Outcome	Outcome	Outcome	Outcome

Case Study Scenario #1	Client Population Element (Case #)	Expected Behaviors	Client/Staff/Partner Element (Case #)	Client
Recognize cues	Recognize cues	Recognize cues	Recognize cues	Recognize cues

Case Study Scenario #2	Client Population Element (Case #)	Expected Behaviors	Client/Staff/Partner Element (Case #)	Client
Analyze cues	Analyze cues	Analyze cues	Analyze cues	Analyze cues

Case Study Scenario #3	Client Population Element (Case #)	Expected Behaviors	Client/Staff/Partner Element (Case #)	Client
Plan	Plan	Plan	Plan	Plan

Case Study Scenario #4	Client Population Element (Case #)	Expected Behaviors	Client/Staff/Partner Element (Case #)	Client
Implement	Implement	Implement	Implement	Implement

Case Study Scenario #5	Client Population Element (Case #)	Expected Behaviors	Client/Staff/Partner Element (Case #)	Client
Evaluate	Evaluate	Evaluate	Evaluate	Evaluate

Case Study Scenario #6	Client Population Element (Case #)	Expected Behaviors	Client/Staff/Partner Element (Case #)	Client
Outcome	Outcome	Outcome	Outcome	Outcome

Some Non-statistical Validation

Cognitive Labs & Useability

Cognitive Labs

- Study cognitive processes SMEs use when evaluating the CJ scenarios & work through items
- Inform early scenario & item development prior to small pilot & larger-scale field testing
- Goals:
 - Validate the authenticity of the scenario & item rationale
 - Do new items measure the intended CJ construct?
 - Is the item/response design easily understood & easy to use (intuitive use)?
 - Correspondence between SME intention and participant responses
 - Strategies employed to evaluate items
 - Thought process when engaging item
 - Does the participant express rationales for the item that correspond to the intended CJ element(s)?
 - Evaluate the information search process
 - Evaluate the extent to which the response set matches their initial conceptualization
 - Help in development of task model for item writing

Cognitive Labs

- Participants: 18 Clinical educator & clinical RNs
- Method:
 - Semi-structured interviews
 - Think aloud protocols
 - Concurrent: used during real-time interaction
 - Retrospective: after interaction to provide reflective feedback
 - Debrief after session for overall feedback
- Sessions recorded for review and archive
- All information used to inform later sessions

Cognitive Labs Framework

Example: Concurrent Questions

1. *Tell me what you did to get your answer to this question.*

Probe as needed with: What in the question made you do that?

Exploring coding strategy (mark as many as apply):

- Used steps in Layer 2 of Clinical Judgement model (formed hypothesis, refined hypothesis, evaluated outcomes)
- Performed steps in Layer 3 of Forming Hypotheses (recognized cues, analyzed cues)
- Performed steps in Layer 3 of Refining Hypotheses (prioritize hypotheses, generate solutions)
- Performed steps in Layer 3 of Evaluation (take actions, evaluate outcomes)
- Discussed the following underlying clinical judgement concepts:

- Discussed the limitation of cues, hypotheses or evaluation
- Made an explicit reference to one or more of the related factors from Layer 4 (environment, medical records, patient observation, experience, specialty, cultural considerations, consequences and risks)
- Recalled prior knowledge. Describe: _____
- Relied on previous question [indicated item dependence]
- Other, describe: _____

Usability Studies

- Goal:
 - Minimize/eliminate construct irrelevant variance:
 - Item presentation that interferes with understanding the content of the item
 - Response structure that interferes with ease of use of items
 - Instruction set that interferes with understanding what is being asked to do
 - Evaluate the memorability of content and response types
- Response types studied:
 - Drag-n-Drop; Cloze/DropDown; Matrix MR/MC; Constructed Response; Hot Spot/Highlight
- 2 studies were undertaken
 - Lead by UX and Psychometric teams
 - All items to be reviewed by at least 5 participants
 - All sessions recorded (WebEx & videotape) for archive and review

Procedures

- Standard instruction set
- Encouraged to talk aloud and describe their thinking when interacting with the prototype items
 - Documented observations
 - Focus only on design & response structures
- At the end of each item interaction: Recall item content and response structure (immediate recall)
- At the end of the session: Recall as much of the item and response structures as they could from the entire session (short-term recall)
- Items that had identifiable issues were pulled from rotation and refactored to overcome participant objections, and put back in rotation

Long-term Memorability Design

- A subset of participants were asked to return after the initial session to review new and refactored items
- Asked to recall as much as they could from previous session(s)
- However, they were also presented with variations on some of the items they had previously seen to gauge long-term recall of item content and response structures
- Design: Alter 3 main aspects of previously viewed items
 - Content: Same/Different
 - Item Type: Same/Different
 - Response Type: Same/Different

Participants

- All participants were nursing students from urban & suburban nursing schools in the Chicago area
- Wave 1:
 - 30 1st round participants reviewed items for design and cognitive features
 - 15 returned for a 2nd round & 8 returned for 3rd round
 - 70 items studied
- Wave 2:
 - 23 1st round participants reviewed items for design and cognitive features
 - 11 new participants
 - 12 returners from Wave 1 (used for long-term recall)
 - 15 returned for a 2nd round and 7 returned for 3rd round
 - 24 new items studied & 12 wave 1 items (both memorability and validate design)

Usability Studies General Findings

- Feel items are difficult
 - Understand what is being asked and how to respond to the items
 - Instruction sets were validated
- Response types highly memorable
- Only vague aspects of the content was memorable for long-term
- Constructed response was most problematic of all
 - No clear resolution was obtained due to multiple competing issues and no consensus among participants on how to overcome issues

Questions?